

HARMONISED PRACTICES, REGULATIONS AND STANDARDS
IN WASTE MANAGEMENT AND DECOMMISSIONING

Deliverable D3.1

**Prioritization of identified
topics: WP3 – Cross Border
Services / Facilities**

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ABSTRACT

Work package 3 aims to identify the most important needs and challenges for Cross Border Services/Facilities for radioactive waste management activities across Europe.

This deliverable presents an overview of the prioritization process undertaken, which include stakeholder engagement, result in the identification of the 3 topics to be taken forward in this project.

The 3 topics which are deemed to be the highest priority are (i) harmonisation of Individual EU and international countries problematic waste inventory, (ii) to align wastes with treatment technologies in a manner acceptable to all stakeholders, (iii) Member States approach to dealing with radioactive contaminated hazardous waste differs.

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Prioritization of identified topics: WP3 – Cross Border Services / Facilities

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Prioritization of identified topics: WP3 – Cross Border Services / Facilities

Version history

Version	Date	Author	Comments
V1	16.06.2023	David Oxberry	Issued for comment to WP3 partners

Prioritization of identified topics: WP3 – Cross Border Services / Facilities

OBJECTIVE

Work package 3 aims to identify the most important needs and challenges for Cross Border Services/Facilities for radioactive waste management activities across Europe. Following the identification of these needs and challenges, the aim is to find ways to overcome them resulting in a series of recommendations and actions.

Task 3.1 is focused on the prioritisation of needs and opportunities for cross-border service/facility considerations (Phase 1a) to define themes to be proposed for deeper analysis in Phase 2.

Deliverable 3.1 presents an overview of the process undertaken to identify and finalise the list of topics following refinement of the topics and Stakeholder engagement in Phase 1.

Prioritization of identified topics: WP3 – Cross Border Services / Facilities

IDENTIFICATION OF TOPICS

The challenges and needs identified in the proposal phase were discussed with the WP3 team members in November, 2022. In addition, the Gap Analysis was conducted in the framework of WP2.

The first list of challenges and needs has been integrated with suggestions and comments from WP3 Partners and with the recommendations extracted from the gap analysis.

The final list was then grouped in 4 main topics covering:

- Best Practice,
- Harmonisation,
- Technical Challenges,
- Geological Disposal Facility (GDF) / Waste Storage Facilities

The topics are summarised in the following table where the different challenges/needs/issues/recommendations are reported together with their origin.

The topics were discussed within WP3 and a finalised list was presented to the Stakeholder community and this list of topics can be found in Table 1 below. Feedback from the Stakeholders was used alongside a selection methodology to define the Needs/Challenges to be further addressed in the HARPERS project. This helped to ensure that the selected topics are well defined and take into consideration any specific areas/activities in their execution in the project such as technical/technology, regulatory, social sciences and other aspects needed.

Prioritization of identified topics: WP3 – Cross Border Services / Facilities

CATEGORY	TOPIC n.	WHAT (Challenge/Need)
Harmonisation	1	Harmonisation of Individual EU and international countries problematic waste inventory
	2	What services are wanted/what is the benefit of centralised treatment facilities.
	3	Standardisation of quality control of suppliers and waste packages
	4	To align wastes with treatment technologies in a manner acceptable to all stakeholders
	5	A need for a common system for waste classification
Best Practice	6	Economical: Centralised vs decentralised characterisation and waste treatment review
	7	Member States approach to dealing with radioactive contaminated hazardous waste differs
	8	Share operational/regulator feedback (both good and bad) from waste treatment facilities
	9	Encouragement in cooperation to improve the safe management of radioactive wastes through building public trust and confidence in the decision-making process for hosting waste treatment facilities.
Technical Challenges	10	Methods of waste characterisation for declaration (transportation, treatment)
	11	Identify gaps & opportunities in current treatment facility needs/operations (Cross-border or mobile/modular)
	12	Identify common EU challenging materials and waste streams
Geological Disposal Facility (GDF) and Waste Storage Facilities	13	Standardise GDF and interim costing approach across MS.
	14	Sharing of intermediate waste storage facilities between MS.

Table 1 – WP3 topics presented to the Stakeholder community for their reaction.

Prioritization of identified topics: WP3 – Cross Border Services / Facilities

INVOLVEMENT OF STAKEHOLDER COMMUNITY

A variety of stakeholders were identified and engaged during the two workshops held in January and March 2023. They represent a wide range of stakeholders from regulators, waste holders/end users, industry and academia.

Workshops

Two workshops were held, inviting stakeholders, to receive their input och the topics evolved during the initial analysis made by HARPERS, using several different sources.

The first workshop used SLIDO Q&A and polling platform to collect the participants response and the second used questionnaire that the participants submitted replies to. There were totally 51 participants, 29 in the first workshop and 22 in the second. The number of participant replies/comments/input to the different questions/polls varied from 49 to 21.

The topics list was presented to the participants in the invitation:

ANNEX 1 - List of Topics (challenges/needs) grouped into 4 main Categories

Prioritization of identified topics: WP3 – Cross Border Services / Facilities

CATEGORY	TOPIC	WHAT (Challenge/Need)	WHY
Harmonisation	1	Harmonisation of Individual EU and international countries problematic waste inventory	Provides EU with data to produce a strategy to efficiently treat problematic wastes before long term storage. This should focus on problematic or challenging wastes that do not have a treatment solution already.
	2	What services are wanted/what is the benefit of centralised treatment facilities.	Inventory harmonisation can lead to increased treatment opportunities.
	3	Standardisation of quality control of suppliers and waste packages	If a standard QC process for waste packages is agreed across the EU, this will reduce mis consignments etc.
	4	To align wastes with treatment technologies in a manner acceptable to all stakeholders	A common understanding of the suitability of treatment options for different waste types is required to establish new shared waste processing opportunities. Noting that stakeholders may have differing views on the suitability of treatment options for certain wastes.
	5	A need for a common system for waste classification	Developing a common system for waste classification is a preliminary harmonization action. Could lead to implementation of potential cross-border services.
	6	Not / Very Low Interest in this Category	

CATEGORY	TOPIC	WHAT (Challenge/Need)	WHY
Best Practice	7	Economical: Centralised vs decentralised characterisation and waste treatment review	Harmonisation of packaging or treatment across EU will lead to economic and storage benefits.
	8	MS approach to dealing with radioactive contaminated hazardous waste differs	Emerging Radioactive contaminated hazardous waste streams may require cross border technical solutions.
	9	Share operational/regulator feedback (both good and bad) from waste treatment facilities	Gathering data from waste management facilities will improve new facility or services lines.

Prioritization of identified topics: WP3 – Cross Border Services / Facilities

	10	Encouragement in cooperation to improve the safe management of radioactive wastes through building public trust and confidence in the decision-making process for hosting waste treatment facilities.	Public perception of cross border waste treatment varies between MS and the benefits to the community that cross border services facilities can bring could result in further cultural benefits to society.
	11	Not / Very Low Interest in this Category	

CATEGORY	TOPIC	WHAT (Challenge/Need)	WHY
Technical Challenges	12	Methods of waste characterisation for declaration (transportation, treatment)	Declarations are sometimes unclear or not trusted, harmonisation of approaches/standards could be used to overcome this.
	13	Identify gaps & opportunities in current treatment facility needs/operations (Cross-border or mobile/modular)	Holistic review of existing facilities will demonstrate a need for additional facilities and identify possible locations based on inventory and possible provision of common treatment and conditioning schemes.
	14	Identify common EU challenging materials and waste streams	Country by Country review of waste streams will underpin a strategy for future cross border treatment facilities.
	15	Not / Very Low Interest in this Category	

CATEGORY	TOPIC	WHAT (Challenge/Need)	WHY
Geological Disposal Facility (GDF) and Waste Storage Facilities	16	Standardise GDF and interim costing approach across MS.	Underpinning of GDF budgets necessary to standardise the EU GDF approach and requirements and might sign post to centralised facility needs.
	17	Sharing of intermediate waste storage facilities between MS.	Not all MS will/should have intermediate storage facilities if their inventories are small or there are additional benefits for all MS to share intermediate storage facilities.
	18	Not / Very Low Interest in this Category	

Prioritization of identified topics: WP3 – Cross Border Services / Facilities

Three open questions were presented to the participants, with the aim to support the prioritization and to reveal any potential topic that HARPERS may have missed.

The questions were:

- What are the main benefits of cross border services/facilities for Radioactive Waste?
- What is the single most important need for you? Can be a current topic or a new one.
- What is the single most difficult barrier stopping cross border services, as you see it?

The AGENDA was the same for both workshops:

ANNEX 2 – HARPERS WP3 online Workshop Agenda

10.00-10.05 Workshop Opening

WP3 Leader (M. Karlsson - Studsvik)

10.05-10.15 General introduction HARPERS Project

Project Coordinator (R. Szóke - IFE)

10.15-10.30 Participants Self Introduction

Moderator: M. Karlsson (Studsvik)

10.30-10.50 Part 1 - Cross Border Services and Facilities for Managing Radioactive Waste

Activities: Introduction + Slido Polls

M. Karlsson (Studsvik)

10.50-11.10 Q&A - Open Discussion

Moderator: M. Karlsson (Studsvik)

Support: P. Konneus (Studsvik) and W. Eek (Studsvik)

11.10-11.15 Break

11.15-11.35 Part 2 - Cross Border Services and Facilities for Managing Radioactive Waste

Activities: Topic Description + Slido Polls

M. Karlsson (Studsvik)

11.35-11.55 Q&A - Open Discussion

Moderator: M. Karlsson (Studsvik)

Support: P. Konneus (Studsvik) and W. Eek (Studsvik)

11.55-12.00 Closure of the Workshop

M. Karlsson (Studsvik)

Workshop results – open question

The main outcome from the open questions are:

- 1) There was no indication that HARPERS missed any topic identified in the initial analysis

Prioritization of identified topics: WP3 – Cross Border Services / Facilities

- 2) The main drivers identified from the questionnaire/polls are confirmed by the outcome from the open questions:
- financial (efficiency)
 - regulatory (to be read as lack of harmonization between the different organizations/players in the member states)
 - societal (public trust and confidence, stakeholder issues)

Question 1

What are the main benefits of cross border services/facilities for Radioactive Waste

	WS1	WS2
Economical	7	3
Efficiency (share)	11	7
Ability to treat waste for all MS., sustainability	3	6

Three areas stand out

- Efficiency (share)
- Economical
- Ability to treat waste for all MS., sustainability

Prioritization of identified topics: WP3 – Cross Border Services / Facilities

What are the main benefits of cross border services/facilities for Radioactive Waste? Share
Wordcloud Poll 36 responses 22 participants

Question 2

What is the single most important need for you?

	WS1	WS2
Experience exc.	3	3
Waste routes and minimization	6	3
Availability	4	4

Three areas stand out

- Waste routes and minimization
- Availability
- Experience exchange

 What is the single most important need for you? Can be a current topic or a new one. One or two short statements please.

 Share

Wordcloud Poll
📄 16 responses
👥 16 participants

Question 3

What is the single most difficult barrier stopping cross border services, as you see it?

	WS1	WS2
Regulatory	10	3
Public	5	4

Two areas stand out

- Regulatory aspects (lack of harmonization)
- Public acceptance, opinion, etc

Prioritization of identified topics: WP3 – Cross Border Services / Facilities

Workshop results – list of topics

The result from SLIDO were:

Prioritization of identified topics: WP3 – Cross Border Services / Facilities

Prioritization of identified topics: WP3 – Cross Border Services / Facilities

Prioritization of identified topics: WP3 – Cross Border Services / Facilities

The summary from both workshops, using the same methodology as with SLIDO (% of votes for a topic within each category) are:

CATEGORY	TOPIC n.	WHAT (Challenge/Need)	WHY	WS2 %	WS1 %
Harmonisation	1	Harmonisation of Individual EU and international countries problematic waste inventory	Provides EU with data to produce a strategy to efficiently treat problematic wastes before long term storage. This should focus on problematic or challenging wastes that do not have a treatment solution already.	8%	20%
	2	What services are wanted/what is the benefit of centralised treatment facilities.	Inventory harmonisation can lead to increased treatment opportunities.	42%	20%
	3	Standardisation of quality control of suppliers and waste packages	If a standard QC process for waste packages is agreed across the EU, this will reduce mis consignments etc.	17%	16%
	4	To align wastes with treatment technologies in a manner acceptable to all stakeholders	A common understanding of the suitability of treatment options for different waste types is required to establish new shared waste processing opportunities. Noting that stakeholders may have differing views on the suitability of treatment options for certain wastes.	25%	27%
	5	A need for a common system for waste classification	Developing a common system for waste classification is a preliminary harmonization action. Could lead to implementation of potential cross-border services.	8%	16%
	6	Not / Very Low Interest in this Category		0%	0%

Prioritization of identified topics: WP3 – Cross Border Services / Facilities

CATEGORY	TOPIC n.	WHAT (Challenge/Need)	WHY		
Technical Challenges	12	Methods of waste characterisation for declaration (transportation, treatment)	Declarations are sometimes unclear or not trusted, harmonisation of approaches/standards could be used to overcome this.	67%	17%
	13	Identify gaps & opportunities in current treatment facility needs/operations (Cross-border or mobile/modular)	Holistic review of existing facilities will demonstrate a need for additional facilities and identify possible locations based on inventory and possible provision of common treatment and conditioning schemes.	8%	58%
	14	Identify common EU challenging materials and waste streams	Country by Country review of waste streams will underpin a strategy for future cross border treatment facilities.	25%	25%
	15	Not / Very Low Interest in this Category		0%	0%

CATEGORY	TOPIC n.	WHAT (Challenge/Need)	WHY	WS2 %	WS1 %
Best Practice	7	Economical: Centralised vs decentralised characterisation and waste treatment review	Harmonisation of packaging or treatment across EU will lead to economic and storage benefits.	25%	8%
	8	Member States approach to dealing with radioactive contaminated hazardous waste differs	Emerging Radioactive contaminated hazardous waste streams may require cross border technical solutions	25%	22%
	9	Share operational/regulator feedback (both good and bad) from waste treatment facilities	Gathering data from waste management facilities will improve new facility or services lines.	33%	27%
	10	Encouragement in cooperation to improve the safe management of radioactive wastes through building public trust and confidence in the decision-making process for hosting waste treatment facilities.	Public perception of cross border waste treatment varies between MS and the benefits to the community that cross border services facilities can bring could result in further cultural benefits to society.	17%	43%
	11	Not / Very Low Interest in this Category		0%	0%

CATEGORY	TOPIC n.	WHAT (Challenge/Need)	WHY	WS2 %	WS1 %
Technical Challenges	12	Methods of waste characterisation for declaration (transportation, treatment)	Declarations are sometimes unclear or not trusted, harmonisation of approaches/standards could be used to overcome this.	67%	17%
	13	Identify gaps & opportunities in current treatment facility needs/operations (Cross-border or mobile/modular)	Holistic review of existing facilities will demonstrate a need for additional facilities and identify possible locations based on inventory and possible provision of common treatment and conditioning schemes.	8%	58%
	14	Identify common EU challenging materials and waste streams	Country by Country review of waste streams will underpin a strategy for future cross border treatment facilities.	25%	25%
	15	Not / Very Low Interest in this Category		0%	0%

CATEGORY	TOPIC n.	WHAT (Challenge/Need)	WHY	WS2 %	WS1 %
Geological Disposal Facility (GDF) and Waste Storage Facilities	16	Standardise GDF and interim costing approach across MS.	Underpinning of GDF budgets necessary to standardise the EU GDF approach and requirements and might sign post to centralised facility needs.	17%	21%
	17	Sharing of intermediate waste storage facilities between MS.	Not all MS will/should have intermediate storage facilities if their inventories are small or there are additional benefits for all MS to share intermediate storage facilities.	17%	63%
	18	Not / Very Low Interest in this Category		67%	16%

Workshop prioritization support

The polls revealed (using the sum of the mean value for each workshop):

What are the main challenges/needs associated with cross border services and facilities for radioactive waste management?		Mean
Pick top three and rank from 1 (most important) to 3		
Technological and operational (availability of technologies/facilities),		1,0
Regulatory		1,9
Safety and Environment (e.g. waste processing)		0,5
Economical (cost/benefit)		0,6
Societal (public trust and confidence, stakeholder issues)		1,3
Competence & Skills		0,4
Other – please specify (you can tell in later questionnaire)		0,0

Prioritization of identified topics: WP3 – Cross Border Services / Facilities

Adding the input from the open questions (in order of importance, so financial was regarded to be worth twice of regulatory and also twice of societal):

- financial (efficiency)
- regulatory (to be read as lack of harmonization between the different organizations/players in the member states)
- societal (public trust and confidence, stakeholder issues)

The top three drivers are marked yellow:

What are the main challenges/needs associated with cross border services and facilities for radioactive waste management?			
Pick top three and rank from 1 (most important) to 3		Using threshold	1.0
Technological and operational (availability of technologies/facilities),		0,6	
Regulatory		1,5	
Safety and Environment (e.g. waste processing)		0,3	
Economical (cost/benefit)		1,3	
Societal (public trust and confidence, stakeholder issues)		1,2	
Competence & Skills		0,2	
Other – please specify (you can tell in later questionnaire)		0,0	

Workshop results summary

The fourth category “Geological Disposal Facility (GDF) and Waste Storage Facilities” was removed from further prioritization due to the fact that 60% of the participants found it to be of no interest.

The top three drivers are, in order of importance:

- regulatory (to be read as lack of harmonization between the different organizations/players in the member states)
- financial (efficiency)
- societal (public trust and confidence, stakeholder issues)

The category order of importance are:

- 1) Harmonization
- 2) Best practice
- 3) Technical challenges

PRIORITISATION METHODOLOGY

The process of interaction was established through the two virtual meetings where there was a mixture of open and closed questions used to support the prioritization effort. Questions included:

- What are the main benefits of cross border services/facilities for Radioactive Waste?
- What is the single most important need for you?
- What is the single most difficult barrier stopping cross border services, as you see it?

The results were captured through a series of word clouds as follows:

Wordcloud Poll 22 participants

In addition, there were a number of opportunities for the Stakeholders to identify which of the prioritization topics were important to them / their organisations. All of this data feed into the prioritization methodology.

Prioritization of identified topics: WP3 – Cross Border Services / Facilities

TOPIC PRIORITIZATION PROCESS

A quantified process was undertaken to make the prioritization using the input from the workshops:

1. The fourth category (Geological disposal related topics) was removed from further prioritization based on input from the two workshops.
2. The replies from the workshops were given percentage weight in each remaining category, so that the sum of all replies equals 100%.
3. The two workshop results were compiled, using average for both workshops
4. The results were normalized to one for each category, giving weight factors to each topic in each of the three remaining categories.
5. The number of replies were included to impact the normalized values to new weight factors.
6. Three challenges, derived from the workshops, were used to further refine each of the topics to reach a final importance weight factor:
 - Regulatory
 - Economical (cost/benefit)
 - Societal (public trust and confidence, stakeholder issues)
7. Each topic in the three categories was assigned to all challenge where there was an impact, see example to the right.
8. The final weight value was compiled from the sum of each challenge multiplied with the weight of that topic, for the top six topics:

Prioritization of identified topics: WP3 – Cross Border Services / Facilities

1	Harmonisation of Individual EU and international countries problematic waste inventory	1,3
2	What services are wanted/what is the benefit of centralised treatment facilities.	0,9
4	To align wastes with treatment technologies in a manner acceptable to all stakeholders	2,2
8	Member States approach to dealing with radioactive contaminated hazardous waste differs	1,1
9	Share operational/regulator feedback (both good and bad) from waste treatment facilities	0,8
13	Identify gaps & opportunities in current treatment facility needs/operations (Cross-border or mobile/modular)	0,8

9. The prioritization results for WP3 are as follows:

- To align wastes with treatment technologies in a manner acceptable to all stakeholders.
- Harmonization of Individual EU and international countries problematic waste inventory.
- Member States approach to dealing with radioactive contaminated hazardous waste differs.

10. The Feedback from all participants in the workshops has been incredibly positive and enthusiastic about the approach we have taken and the outcome of the prioritization process. This represents a balanced perspective from industry, academia, regulators and other stakeholders.

Prioritization of identified topics: WP3 – Cross Border Services / Facilities

TOP PRIORITIZED TOPICS

The 3 topics that have been identified to be further developed and assessed in the forthcoming years of the HARPERS project are as follows:

CATEGORY	TOPIC n.	WHAT (Challenge/Need)
Harmonisation	1	Harmonisation of Individual EU and international countries problematic waste inventory
	4	To align wastes with treatment technologies in a manner acceptable to all stakeholders
Best Practice	7	Member States approach to dealing with radioactive contaminated hazardous waste differs

The three chosen topics will be advertised as part of the open calls process in July 2023 which will identify and execute specific proposals to advance our knowledge and understanding in order to support the Harmonisation of cross border services and facilities for the treatment of Radioactive waste.